

NOTES

Viscosity of Potassium Bromide and Sodium Bromide in Dioxan-Water Mixtures at 35°

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The viscosity of Potassium Bromide and Sodium Bromide in dioxane-water mixture of varying compositions were measured. The present work was undertaken with a view to investigate the applicability of the 'Jones Dole' equation to explore the nature of 'B' in the said equation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Potassium Bromide and Sodium Bromide used were of 'E. Merck—Extra pure' quality. Solvents used were dioxane-water mixtures containing 10, 20 and 30% of dioxane by weight. The preparation of the solvent, solution and other experimental procedure has been described previously.¹

TABLE I

Comparison of observed and calculated values of solvent: Dioxane 20% + water 80% by weight)

Electrolyte.	Conc.	η/η_0 (obs)	η/η_0 (Cal)
KBr.	0.0156	1.0019	1.0017
	0.0652	1.0050	1.0051
NaBr.	0.0284	1.0053	1.0050
	0.0556	1.0089	1.0091

TABLE II

Values of A, B and x

Solvent % g dioxane in water.	KBr			NaBr		
	A	B	x	A	B	x
10	0.0057	0.034	1.00	0.0061	0.115	1.00
20	0.0072	0.051	1.00	0.0076	0.124	0.99
30	0.0088	0.062	0.99	0.0100	0.170	0.93

DISCUSSION

The experimental data between the concentration ranges of 0.01*N* to 0.1*N* for the two electrolytes have been examined in the light of the modified Jones-Dole equation² and the values of A, B and 'x' have been estimated in the usual

1. R. C. Acharya, P. K. Das and D. Patnaik; *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 56.
2. D. Patnaik and P. K. Das., *Curr. Sci.*, 1956, **25**, 337.

manner. In the solvent containing 10% of dioxane, the data fit the Jones-Dole equation, whereas the modified Jones-Dole equation is obeyed in solvents containing higher percentage of dioxane. Table I gives the data for the two electrolytes in the solvent containing 20% of dioxane and in table II the values of A, B and x are given. In consistent with the previous measurements^{1,3}, the additive character of B is noticed in solvents containing 10 and 20% of dioxane but fails to show the additivity in the solvent containing 30% of dioxane. Frank and Evans⁴ and Latimar⁵ have analysed the influence of ions on the structure of water and have suggested the existence of a frozen oriented layer of water molecules around the ions and the frozen layer is further surrounded by a diffused layer of solvent molecules where the water structure is broken down. It is consistent to expect that the ordering of water structure or ordering of the solvent molecules in the solvation spheres would lead to increase in the viscosity. McRae⁶ has suggested that dioxane molecule has two nonadjacent dipolar groups whose moments cancel, so that the effective reaction field is probably greater than is indicated by macroscopic properties. If the picture presented by Frank and Evans is kept in view, then in the cases under consideration, the frozen layer around the cations be expected to be constituted of both the water molecules and the dioxane molecules possibly consisting of more of the former than the latter kind of molecules; whereas the diffused layer would consist of loosely oriented water and dioxane molecules, the extent of orientation decreasing with the distance from the ion till the outermost layer has the same structure and composition as that of the solvent. When the dioxane content of the solvent increases, more dioxane molecules take part in constituting the diffused layer and thus promoting a sort of ordering effect in the solvation sphere and exhibiting an increase in the value of 'B' from composition to composition. At the experimental temperature the water structure is almost broken down and the cations contribute very little to breaking down the water structure, on the other hand the greater is the field round an ion, the larger is the ordering effect and hence the larger the value of B. This expectation is justified in showing a larger value of B for sodium bromide than that of potassium bromide in the solvents studied.

3. P. K. Das, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 613.

4. H. S. Frank and M. W. Evans, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, **13**, 507.

5. W. M. Latimar, *Chem. Rev.*, 1936, **18**, 349.

6. E. G. Mc. Rae. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1957, **61**, 552.

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Received, September 8, 1967.